

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
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In Reply Refer to:
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2017-F-0209

Mr. Rick Bottoms, PhD
Attn: Frances Malamud-Roam
Department of the Army
San Francisco District, U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
1455 Market Street, 16th Floor
San Francisco, California 94103-1398

NOV 20 2017

Subject: Biological Opinion on the Tesoro Refining and Marketing Company's (Tesoro) Waste Management Units (WMUs) 10/11/14, 31, and 32 Closure Project at the Golden Eagle Refinery (Refinery) in the City of Martinez, Contra Costa County, California (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers (Corps) file number 2008-00083S)

Dear Dr. Bottoms:

This letter is in response to the Corps' July 16, 2012, request for initiation of formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) for the proposed Tesoro WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32 Closure Project (proposed project) at the Refinery in the City of Martinez, Contra Costa County, California (Corps file number 2008-00083S). Your request was received by the Service on July 17, 2012. At issue are the proposed project's effects on the federally endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*) and endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*). This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR 402).

Recent genetic analyses of rail species resulted in a change in the common name and taxonomy of the large, "clapper-type" rails (*Rallus longirostris*) of the west coast of North America to Ridgway's rail (*Rallus obsoletus*) (Maley and Brumfield 2013, Chesser *et al.* 2014). The change in the common name and taxonomy of the California clapper rail, however, does not change the listing status of the species.

The Federal action on which we are consulting is the Corps' issuance of a permit to Tesoro pursuant to Section 404 of the Clean Water Act of 1972, as amended (33 U.S.C. § 1344 *et seq.*) to place fill in Corps jurisdictional seasonal wetlands to close the former WMUs at the Refinery pursuant to the San Francisco Bay Regional Water Quality Control Board (SFRWQCB) Waste Discharge Requirements (WDR R2-2004-0056) and the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency Administrative Order Resource Conservation and Recovery Act 09-98-0013S. Closure of the WMUs will be conducted by the Avon Remediation Team (ART). ART is a cooperative arrangement between the Refinery owner, Tesoro, and Texaco Downstream Properties Incorporated to address certain legacy environmental compliance requirements. Pursuant to 50

CFR 402.12(j), you submitted a biological assessment for our review and requested concurrence with the findings presented therein. These findings conclude that the proposed project may affect, and is likely to adversely affect the salt marsh harvest mouse, and may affect, but is not likely to adversely affect the California clapper rail.

In considering your request, we based our evaluation on the following: (1) the June 2012 *Section 7 Biological Assessment Waste Management Units 10/11/14, 31, and 32, Golden Eagle Refinery, Martinez, Contra Costa County, California* (WRA Environmental Consultants (WRA) 2012); (2) the November 2013 *Section 7 Biological Assessment Addendum Waste Management Units 10/11/14, 31, and 32, Tesoro Golden Eagle Refinery, Martinez, Contra Costa County, California* (WRA 2013); (3) the January 2017 *Section 7 Biological Assessment WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32, Tesoro Martinez Refinery, Martinez, Contra Costa County, California* (Biological Assessment) (WRA 2017a); (4) the August 26, 2016, letter from WRA to the Corps containing the revised project description (M. Osowski, WRA, *in litt.* 2016a); (5) annual protocol-level surveys for the California clapper rail conducted between 2008 and 2017 (WRA 2008a, 2008c, 2008d, 2009f, 2009g, 2009h, 2011b, 2012b, 2013b, 2014b, 2015, 2016a, 2016b, 2017); (6) the February 10, 2016, letter from WRA to the Service regarding the effects of construction noise (M. Osowski, WRA, *in litt.* 2016b); (7) the January 2015 *Final Cordelia Slough Preserve for Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse and Wetland Enhancement Long-Term Management Plan* (Wildlands 2015); (8) miscellaneous correspondence and electronic mail messages concerning the proposed project among representatives of the Service, the Corps, Tesoro, ART, WRA, Johnson Marigot Consulting, LLC, Morgan, Lewis & Bockius, LLP, and the SFRWQCB; and (9) additional information available to the Service.

The Service does not agree that the proposed project is not likely to adversely affect the California clapper rail. Although no suitable tidal marsh breeding habitat would be directly disturbed, breeding California clapper rails in the adjacent tidal marsh of the Point Edith Wildlife Area may be disturbed by construction noise from the proposed project. An acoustic study conducted for the proposed project shows construction of the proposed project will result in noise levels elevated 8 to 13 decibels above ambient conditions within the adjacent tidal marsh of the Point Edith Wildlife Area (M. Carr, Extant Acoustical Consulting, LLC, *in litt.* 2014) including an area where a California clapper rail was observed in 2009 (WRA 2015).

The remainder of this document provides our biological opinion on the effects of the proposed project on the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

Consultation History

- April - June 2009: The Service communicated with the Corps regarding the proposed project via electronic mail messages and a conference call.
- May 19, 2011: The Service attended a site visit to WMU 32 at the Refinery along with representatives from Tesoro, ART, and WRA to evaluate the potential effects on listed species from the proposed investigations needed at WMU 32 to refine the engineering design for the proposed project.

- January 25, 2012: The Service received from ART a letter requesting technical assistance regarding the proposed ongoing investigations and design studies at WMU 32 needed to refine the engineering design for the proposed project.
- April 12, 2012: The Service sent a technical assistance letter to ART stating that with the implementation of the proposed avoidance and minimization measures the proposed ongoing investigations and design studies at WMU 32 needed to refine the engineering design for the proposed project are not likely to result in the take of salt marsh harvest mice or California clapper rails (Service file number 08ESMF00-2012-TA-2013-1). The letter also stated that the Corps would initiate formal consultation for the implementation of the proposed project.
- July 17, 2012: The Service received from the Corps the first biological assessment for the proposed project (WRA 2012) and the request for initiation of formal consultation.
- August 21, 2012: The Service sent via electronic mail to the Corps and WRA comments on the first biological assessment and a request for additional information on the proposed project.
- October 30, 2012: The Service attended a conference call for the proposed project to discuss the Service's comments on the first biological assessment.
- February 19, 2013: The Service attended a site visit.
- April 4, 2013: The Service sent a letter to the Corps requesting additional information on the proposed project (Service file number 08ESMF00-2012-TA-2013-2, Service 2013b).
- April 18, 2013: The Service participated in a conference call for the proposed project.
- June 28, 2013: The Service attended a meeting for the proposed project with WRA, Tesoro, and ART.
- August 19, 2013: The Service attended a site visit to the proposed Cordelia Slough Preserve habitat compensation site with staff from ART, Wildlands, and WRA.
- September 16, 2013: The Service received from Wildlands the draft long-term management plan for the proposed Cordelia Slough Preserve habitat compensation site (Wildlands 2013).
- November 12, 2013: The Service received from the Corps a letter containing the addendum to the biological assessment (WRA 2013) and responding to the Service's request for additional information on the proposed project.

- November, 15, 2013: The Service sent via electronic mail to the Corps, Tesoro, ART, WRA, and Wildlands comments on the draft long-term management plan for the proposed Cordelia Slough Preserve habitat compensation site.
- February 10, 2014: The Service attended a site visit to the proposed project site with staff from the Corps, Tesoro, ART, WRA, and SFRWQCB.
- June 6, 2014: The Service received from WRA the acoustic study report evaluating the effects of noise from proposed project construction on California clapper rails in the nearby tidal marshes (M. Carr, Extant Acoustical Consulting, LLC, *in litt.* 2014; B. Clarke, WRA, *in litt.* 2014a).
- June 25, 2014: The Service sent via electronic mail to WRA, Tesoro, ART, and the Corps comments on the acoustics study report.
- June 30, 2014: The Service received from Wildlands the revised draft long-term management plan for the proposed Cordelia Slough Preserve habitat compensation site (Wildlands 2014).
- July 2, 2014: The Service attended a meeting with WRA and ART.
- November 25, 2014: The Service received from WRA responses to the Service's comments on the acoustics study report (B. Clarke, WRA, *in litt.* 2014b).
- February 6, 2015: The Service approved the final long-term management plan for the Cordelia Slough Preserve habitat compensation site (WRA 2015).
- February 17, 2016: The Service received from WRA the acoustic monitoring proposal for monitoring the effects of noise from proposed project construction on California clapper rails in the nearby tidal marshes (M. Osowski, WRA, *in litt.* 2016b).
- July 7, 2016: The Service received from WRA the proposed noise minimization measures for the California clapper rail.
- August 26, 2016: The Service received from WRA and the Corps the revised final project description for the proposed project (M. Osowski, WRA, *in litt.* 2016a).
- September 7, 2016: The Service requested from the Corps whether the conservation measures and effects analysis in the biological assessment (WRA 2012, 2013) were still applicable to the revised final project description.
- January 16, 2017: The Service received from WRA the revised Biological Assessment (WRA 2017a).
- January 25, 2017: The Service sent via electronic mail to the Corps, WRA, and ART a request for measures that would be implemented to avoid disturbing breeding California clapper rails and noting that the initially proposed

noise minimization measures were not included in the revised Biological Assessment.

- February 8, 2017: The Service received from WRA a letter disagreeing with the Service's response that breeding California clapper rails could be disturbed by noise associated with construction of the proposed project.
- April 10, 2017: The Service participated in a conference call with WRA and the Corps to discuss the potential for the proposed project to disturb breeding California clapper rails and measures to minimize the effects.
- May 15, 2017: The Service received the memorandum from WRA summarizing their conclusion that construction work during the breeding season would not disturb breeding California clapper rails.
- May 31, 2017: The Service participated in a conference call with WRA, Tesoro, ART, and the Corps regarding the potential for proposed breeding season construction work to disturb breeding California clapper rails. The Service summarized their position that a breeding pair of California clapper rails may be harassed due to elevated construction noise during the six-year construction period due to the known occurrence of a California clapper rail within less than 500 feet of the proposed work area within the past nine years. The Service stated that if ART cannot agree to avoid construction within 700 feet of California clapper rails during the rail's breeding season, then ART should compensate by funding the restoration and/or preservation of a breeding territory for the California clapper rail at a Service-approved location.
- June 8, 2017: The Service received from WRA the California clapper rail protocol-level survey results for the 2017 breeding season (WRA 2017b).
- June 29, 2017: The Service received from Johnson Marigot Consulting, LLC a memorandum summarizing the benefits of the proposed remediation work on the California clapper rail (C. Johnson, Johnson Marigot Consulting, LLC, *in litt.* 2017).
- July 5, 2017: The Service participated in a conference call with WRA, Tesoro, ART, Johnson Marigot Consulting, LLC, Morgan, Lewis & Bockius, LLP and the Corps to discuss the memorandum from Johnson Marigot Consulting, LLC (C. Johnson, Johnson Marigot Consulting, LLC, *in litt.* 2017). WRA, Tesoro, ART, and Johnson Marigot Consulting, LLC, agreed to contact the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge to discuss options for habitat compensation for the California clapper rail by funding habitat restoration at the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge.
- August 10, 2017: The Service received a letter from Morgan, Lewis & Bockius, LLP describing ART's proposal to fund the restoration of 5.5 acres of tidal marsh habitat for the California clapper rail through channel excavation and creation of marsh mounds in the Sonoma Creek Marsh Enhancement

Project at the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge as offsite compensatory mitigation for the effects of the proposed project on the California clapper rail (E. Gannon, Morgan, Lewis & Bockius, LLP, *in litt.* 2017).

- August 14, 2017: The Service attended a meeting with staff from Tesoro, ART, Johnson Marigot Consulting, LLC, and Morgan, Lewis & Bockius, LLP, to discuss the August 10, 2017, letter from Morgan, Lewis & Bockius, LLP, and avoidance and minimization measures for the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail. ART agreed to contribute \$357,500 to the Sonoma Creek Marsh Enhancement Project at the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge as offsite compensatory mitigation for the effects of the proposed project on the California clapper rail. ART requested a draft biological opinion.
- August 16, 2017: The Service received a request for a draft biological opinion from the Corps.
- September 29, 2017: The Service sent the draft biological opinion to the Corps.
- November 14, 2017: The Service received comments on the draft biological opinion from the Corps.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The proposed project includes field investigation and field design studies for closure of the WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32 at the Refinery, WMU closure construction, and post-closure monitoring and maintenance in the action area. The map of the proposed project area is shown in Figure 1 below.

WMUs Closure Summary

WMUs 10/11/14 – Consolidation of Wastes and Capping at WMU 14 under a Title 27 Prescriptive Cover

Closure at WMUs 10/11/14 involves consolidating the waste material from WMUs 10 and 11 (approximately 83,000 cubic yards) into WMU 14. WMUs 10 and 11 will subsequently be considered clean closed by the removal of wastes to the limit of visible impacts down into the top of the underlying coke fill layer. The excavated waste deposited into WMU 14 (along with select wastes from other WMU closures) will then be covered with a prescriptive Title 27 multi-layer soil cap, which is likely to include a geomembrane. Prior to placement into WMU 14, the excavated waste materials will be stabilized with additional soil or cement to improve their handling and compaction characteristics. The perimeter berms at WMU 14 will be improved to support the consolidated waste material and cap for stability and settlement. The excavations resulting from the waste consolidation will be backfilled with clean soil and revegetated to restore the impacted sensitive habitat in accordance with a habitat mitigation and monitoring

plan (HMMP). The erosion-resistant surface of the WMU 14 cap will be un-vegetated (*i.e.*, covered with gravel and rock).

WMU 31 – Clean Closure and Relocation of Wastes to WMU 14

Waste at WMU 31 will be excavated down to the limits of visible impacts in the underlying and adjacent soil (approximately 111,000 cubic yards of waste) and relocated to WMU 14 for final capping. WMU 31 will then be considered clean closed. The waste excavations will be backfilled

Figure 1. The action area and proposed project features (copied from Figure 4 in WRA 2017a).

with clean soil to approximately pre-excitation grades and re-vegetated. Wetlands and upland habitat at WMU 31 impacted by excavation activities will be restored after construction.

WMU 32 – Engineered Alternative Low-Permeability Cover

The WMU footprint will be covered with a Title 27 Compliant cap and cover which is likely to include a geomembrane.

Construction Process

Field Investigations and Field Design Studies

Field investigations to further refine the nature and extent of waste, and surface and subsurface conditions at the action area will be conducted. The field investigations may include sampled soil borings, test pits, and installation and sampling of groundwater monitoring wells or similar devices. These investigations may involve the use of hand-operated power tools, truck-mounted drill rigs, backhoes, and support vehicles. These investigations will also involve the construction of temporary vehicular and personnel access ways, such as crane mats and marsh mats, and corridors through vegetated areas.

Field-scale engineering design studies will be conducted within the action area. Such studies may include small-scale excavations, test fill placements, and pilot-scale waste stabilization and geotechnical constructions (*e.g.*, test soil/cement column installations). These field design studies may involve the use of hand-operated power tools, truck-mounted drill rigs, a variety of earth moving vehicles (such as excavators), other heavy construction equipment, and support vehicles. These activities will also involve the construction of temporary vehicular and personnel access ways such as earthen roads, crane mats, marsh mats, and corridors through vegetated areas. The design studies may result in constructed features, such as ground improvement soil-cement columns, that will be incorporated into the later closure construction.

Site Preparation

Prior to excavation activities in the WMUs, the excavation areas will be grubbed to remove rocks, vegetation, and debris. Monitoring wells located within the work zone will be destroyed in accordance with Contra Costa County well destruction requirements. Utilities will be relocated where necessary. The existing storm water control pipes along the interior berms of WMU 10/11/14 will be removed. Overhead power lines in WMUs 31 and 32 may be relocated if necessary. Best management practices (BMPs) will be implemented to minimize erosion and sedimentation. Possible BMPs include, but are not limited to, silt fencing, straw wattles, and watering. Access to the action area will be controlled with temporary fencing or similar methods.

Access Roads

Temporary access roads will be constructed to allow construction equipment to approach excavation operations and other on-WMU work zones. Some of the access roads will be incorporated into the WMU closure design for permanent post-closure access as well. WMU 14 perimeter berms will be improved and surfaced with gravel for the purposes described above. At least one permanent access road will be constructed at WMU 31. The access road will likely be

located west of the Clean Water Canal. At a minimum, significant soil improvement using geosynthetic reinforcement and/or soil stabilizing ground improvement and shoring will be required to support construction traffic.

Excavation and Relocation/Consolidation of Wastes

The WMU 31 Oily Skim Pond will be excavated during the construction of the adjacent access road. Sheet pile shoring may be utilized at the Oily Skim Pond to protect the open excavation and adjacent equipment areas. Following waste excavation of the Oily Skim Pond and the south end of Dredged Sediment Area 1, excavation will proceed in the Dredged Sediment Areas.

WMU 31 excavation and backfill operations in the Dredged Sediment Areas will generally proceed from the north to the south. Where conditions warrant, geosynthetic fabric may be placed prior to backfilling to provide support for the import backfill soils. Temporary sheet piling may be used for excavation shoring. As excavation progresses, backfill will be placed to pre-excavation grades, thereby facilitating re-establishment of the temporarily impacted wetlands and habitat. Excavation will be conducted in phases in discrete areas to reduce the overall temporal disturbance of temporary impacts.

Because the waste material tends to be very soft and much of it is located below the groundwater table, the excavated material from WMUs 10, 11, 31, and 32 will need to be stabilized prior to further handling by removal of liquid or by the addition of a reinforcing material (e.g., soil or cement). The waste material from the Oily Skim Pond will either be similarly processed before transport to WMU 14 for final capping or sent to the Refinery coker unit for recycling. Measures such as misters and foam application may be used for odor control during waste excavation and stabilizing work in the WMUs.

Soil Cap Construction

WMU 14 Cap

In situ soil-cement mixing to control the stability and settlement of the subsequent consolidated waste and final cap will be performed underneath the perimeter berms of WMU 14 to an average depth of approximately 20 feet. The perimeter berms will be raised to approximately 20 feet above mean sea level for the cap construction and surfaced with aggregate base for erosion control and for post-closure access. The cap will be placed above the consolidated waste material. The cap will consist of a Title 27 compliant cap and cover including a geomembrane. The final cover will be constructed at an elevation of approximately 40 feet above mean sea level.

WMU 32 Cap

The soil cap construction at WMU 32 will consist of a Title 27 compliant cap and cover including a geomembrane potentially extending beyond the southwest perimeter of the WMU.

Restoration of Temporarily Affected Areas

Excavated areas that lie outside of the caps will be backfilled and graded for surface water drainage or will be used to re-create wetlands impacted by excavation activities. Non-wetland areas will be restored through seeding and planting native upland grasses and shrubs. Temporarily impacted wetlands will be restored through planting native brackish seasonal wetland plant species. A separate HMMP that details re-vegetation activities and monitoring at each location will be submitted to the Corps, the Service, and SFRWQCB.

Post Closure Monitoring and Maintenance

Groundwater Monitoring

Monitoring of the closed WMUs will include the installation and periodic sampling of groundwater monitoring wells. Installation, maintenance, sampling, and repair of groundwater monitoring wells will be performed from permanent access roadways and developed access areas.

Closed Unit Inspection, Maintenance, and Repair

The caps of the closed WMUs will be regularly inspected, maintained, and repaired/upgraded in accordance with SFRWQCB-approved Closure and Post-Closure Maintenance Plans. Inspections will take place from permanent roadways and access areas where caps and/or land covers have been constructed. Anticipated maintenance and repair activities will include keeping erosion control surfaces and surface water drainage ways clear and in good condition, repairs to signage, gates, and fences, monitoring device repair, and removal of invasive plant species. Minor repairs to the structures mentioned above will require the use of hand and power tools. Major repairs may be performed in the event of erosion or damage to the cap under Title 27 and SFRWQCB Waste Discharge Requirements; major repairs may necessitate the use of heavy equipment. Upgrades to berm heights, armor layers, and access roads may result from adaptive management responses to sea level rise. Areas of inspection, maintenance, and repair will be accessed using developed areas such as roads, as described above.

Restoration Maintenance

Restoration maintenance will include non-native plant management, irrigation system use, and additional planting of native vegetation as necessary. Maintenance of the restoration area will be conducted using hand tools and aquatic-safe herbicides. Monitoring and maintenance of restored wetlands and habitat will be conducted under the terms and conditions outlined in the forthcoming HMMP for the duration of the prescribed monitoring period.

Equipment

Standard construction equipment will be used in the closure actions described above, as well as preceding field design studies. Field investigation activities may use excavators, front end loaders, hand-operated power equipment, truck-mounted drilling equipment, and support trucks. Marsh mats, crane mats, and similar devices will provide temporary access to investigation design study areas.

Sheet piles, required to support access roads in WMU 31 and in some excavation areas, will be driven by impact or vibratory hammers mounted on a crane or other mobile heavy equipment. Hydraulic press equipment may also be appropriate for sheet pile installation. Ground improvement may require specialized drilling equipment for soil mixing. Ground improvement materials, such as cement and water, will require mixing equipment and associated staging areas and/or structures.

Excavation and backfilling will be performed with excavators, bulldozers, and graders, with earth moved by front end loaders and dump trucks. Construction of the cover systems may use the aforementioned equipment in addition to other fine-grading and compaction equipment. Areas of restored habitat will use grading equipment. Vacuum trucks, pumps, holding tanks, and similar equipment will support excavation and waste removal activities. Water trucks will be used to suppress dust.

Maintenance and minor repairs to caps will require hand-operated power tool use and relatively light construction equipment (*e.g.*, backhoes and light truck access). Heavy equipment, such as drill rigs and development rigs, will be used to install groundwater monitoring devices.

Non-native invasive plant species removal on caps and/or land cover and restored areas will require power tool use (*e.g.*, mowers and string trimmers), hand tool use, and the use of herbicides.

Construction Duration

All activities described above could occur at any time throughout the calendar year. Work will be mainly performed during daylight hours, although work lighting may be used to extend the length of work days, if necessitated by the activity, the project schedule, or for worker safety. Project construction activities will begin upon receipt of various regulatory permits. Closure activities in the action area near the WMUs will proceed as efficiently and expeditiously as possible, but will likely continue for one to six years depending on location.

Based on the closure concepts described herein, estimates of each WMU's project duration to completion are as follows: WMU 10/11 one year, WMU 14 six years, WMU 31 three years, and WMU 32 one year. Some construction activities will be conducted concurrently, but the construction duration is expected to last approximately six years (2019-2025). Additionally, as described above in the section *Excavation and Relocation/Consolidation of Wastes*, waste removal from WMU 31 will be conducted in phases, where discrete areas are disturbed, excavated, backfilled to pre-excavation grades, and revegetated in less than 24 months. Thus wetlands and upland habitat will be restored similar to pre-disturbance conditions.

Inspection and maintenance of the closed WMUs will continue as required by the SFRWQCB-approved closure plans, assumed to be for an indefinite period of time. Monitoring and potential maintenance of restored habitat will be for the duration of the prescribed monitoring period approved by reviewing agencies in the forthcoming HMMP. No effects from the post-closure monitoring and maintenance activities are anticipated.

Conservation Measures

ART and its contractors will implement the following measures to avoid or minimize potential adverse direct and indirect effects to the salt marsh harvest mouse, California clapper rail, and their habitats within the action area.

1. Construction personnel will receive Service-approved worker environmental awareness training from a Service-approved biologist. The training will include a description of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail, including natural history and habitat, a review of these species listings, general protection measures to be implemented to protect these species, and a delineation of the limits of the work areas.
2. Prior to the commencement of construction, the following measures will be conducted in an effort to ensure no salt marsh harvest mice are present in any work area. Prior to removal of vegetation, the Service-approved biologist will walk the work zone to ensure no salt marsh harvest mice or their nests occur within the work zone. In potential salt marsh harvest mouse habitat areas, vegetation will be removed using a two-step process by which vegetation will be removed to bare ground in a manner to enable and encourage salt marsh harvest mice to move out and away from the construction area. Tall vegetation will first be removed using a walk behind mower with the blade set at a high ground clearance to avoid direct mortality to the salt marsh harvest mouse. This will allow subsequent removal of vegetation to the ground surface using string trimmers under the supervision of a Service-approved biological monitor since visibility of the ground surface will be possible given the short stature of the vegetation.
3. Once vegetation removal is complete, temporary exclusion fencing will be placed around a defined work area prior to the start of construction activities preventing salt marsh harvest mice from moving into construction areas. The fence will be made of a material that does not allow salt marsh harvest mice to pass through or climb over, and the bottom will be buried to a depth of at least 6 inches so salt marsh harvest mice cannot crawl under the fence. All supports for the exclusion fencing will be placed on the inside of the work area. The fences will be inspected daily for holes and gaps, which will be repaired as soon as detected.
4. A Service-approved biologist(s) will be present during installation of exclusion fence, removal of the exclusion fence, vegetation removal, and as needed to conduct environmental awareness training for all construction personnel. The biologist(s) will also be the contact person(s) for any employee or contractor if a salt marsh harvest mouse is encountered on the job.
5. If a salt marsh harvest mouse is encountered during construction, activities within 100 feet of the mouse will cease until the mouse leaves the work area of its own volition, and it has been determined by the biologist that the mouse will not be harmed. If the mouse does not move, the Service-approved biologist will contact the Service for guidance.
6. All food and food-related trash items will be enclosed in sealed trash containers and removed completely from the site at the end of each day.

7. No nighttime work is planned; however, if nighttime work is necessary the applicant will direct the lighting away from potential habitat outside the exclusion fence and use lighting that minimizes backward and side lighting.
8. ART will compensate for the temporary disturbance of 24.64 acres and the permanent loss of 11.27 acres of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat by preserving and managing in perpetuity a total of 83.09 acres of suitable habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse at Wildlands' Cordelia Slough Preserve in Suisun Bay in Solano County, California, under a Service-approved long-term management plan with a fully funded endowment (Wildlands 2015). The amount of habitat compensation is based on a ratio of 2:1 for temporary impacts (less than 24 months in duration) and a 3:1 ratio for permanent impacts (longer than 24 months in duration).
9. The potential for the contamination and degradation of suitable habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse will be minimized by implementing water quality BMPs, a Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan, emergency spill containment and contingency plan, and weed management.
10. All temporarily disturbed habitats within the action area will be restored under a Service-approved HMMP with success criteria and invasive plant species control.
11. ART will fund \$357,500 for the restoration of at least 5.5 acres of tidal marsh/high tide refuge habitat for the California clapper rail through channel excavation and creation of marsh mounds in the Sonoma Creek Marsh Enhancement Project at the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge in Sonoma County, California (Wetlands and Water Resources, Inc. 2009; San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge 2014; Service file number 81420-2011-F-0774-2, Service 2014). ART will provide the funding prior to the initiation of construction of the proposed project.

Action Area

The action area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as "all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action." For the proposed project, the action area encompasses approximately 110 acres, including approximately: 32 acres for WMUs 10/11/14; 8 acres of operational/access areas for WMUs 10/11/14; 30 acres for WMU 31; 20 acres of operational/access areas for WMU 31; 12 acres for WMU 32; and 7 acres of operational/access areas for WMU 32. In addition, the action area includes all suitable tidal marsh breeding habitat for the California clapper rail at the Point Edith Wildlife Area within 700 feet of the proposed project footprint where noise levels will be elevated above ambient conditions due to proposed project construction during the breeding season. The action area also includes the 83.09 acres of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat that will be preserved at Wildlands' Cordelia Slough Preserve in Suisun Bay in Solano County, California. The action area also includes the 5.5 acres of tidal marsh/high tide refuge habitat that will be restored in Sonoma Creek Marsh at the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge in Sonoma County, California. In summary the action area encompasses 198.59 acres including the proposed project and compensatory mitigation areas.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Endangered Species Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably would be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the condition of the species in the action area, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the action area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which determines the direct and indirect impacts of the proposed Federal action and the effects of any interrelated or interdependent activities on the species; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the action area on the species.

Status of the Species

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*). Both subspecies are listed as endangered. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species’ range-wide status, please refer to the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California* (Recovery Plan; http://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP_Final.pdf; Service 2013a). No change in the species’ listing status was recommended in the February 2010 5-year review for the salt marsh harvest mouse (Service 2010). Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document and the Recovery Plan have continued to act on the species since the February 2010 5-year review and the August 2013 Recovery Plan were finalized, with the loss, degradation, and fragmentation of habitat being the most significant effect. While there have been continued losses of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat throughout the various recovery units, including the Suisun Bay Area unit where the proposed project is located, to date no project has proposed a level of effects for which the Service has issued a biological opinion of jeopardy for the species.

California Clapper Rail

For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species’ range-wide status, please refer to the Recovery Plan (http://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP_Final.pdf; Service 2013a). No change in the species’ listing status was recommended in the April 2013 5-year review for the California clapper rail (Service 2013c). Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document and the Recovery Plan have continued to act on the species since the April 2013 5-year review and the August 2013 Recovery Plan were finalized, with predation and the loss, degradation, and fragmentation of habitat being the most significant effect. While there

have been continued losses of California clapper rail habitat throughout the various recovery units, including the Suisun Bay Area unit where the proposed project is located, to date no project has proposed a level of effects for which the Service has issued a biological opinion of jeopardy for the species.

Environmental Baseline

Historical Use of the WMUs

The Refinery originally refined crude oil from the San Joaquin Valley into gasoline, kerosene, and fuel oil. Lubricating oils, grease, solvents, and transformer oils have also been produced during the life of the Refinery. Presently, the Refinery is the second-largest refinery in Northern California with a crude oil capacity of 166,000 barrels per day. The Refinery produces motor fuels, heavy fuel oils, and liquefied petroleum gas from crude oils from Alaskan, Californian, and foreign sources.

WMUs 10 and 11 are inactive waste management units. They were constructed in approximately 1966. These treatment units received oily wastes and petroleum sludge from various Refinery facilities. Waste placement in WMUs 10 and 11 ceased in approximately 1976. Land farming operations occurred on WMUs 10 and 11 from the late 1970s until 1991 (a bioremediation treatment process that is performed in the upper soil zone or in biotreatment cells; contaminated soils, sediments or sludges are incorporated into the soil surface and periodically turned over or tilled to aerate the mixture). Thereafter, biological treatment of the wastes was allowed to continue in a passive mode.

WMU 14 is an inactive waste management unit constructed over the western portion of WMU 10 in 1976. WMU 14 is made up of four sludge-drying beds that received sludge from biologically treated Refinery wastewater until approximately 1988. Ongoing maintenance activities that occur in WMUs 10/11/14 consist of application of rolled erosion control blanket to prevent surface erosion in an effort to prevent exposure to waste material and maintenance of WMU berms, when necessary.

WMU 31 is an inactive waste management unit that was previously diked and used for disposal of dredge spoils and oily wastes as early as the 1920s. WMU 31 is subdivided by constructed berms into four distinct topographic basins. The northern three basins likely received dredge spoils from Pacheco Creek, the Clean Water Canal, and excavated materials from the construction of the Bio- Oxidation Pond. These areas were also reportedly used for disposal of oily wastes and leaded gasoline as early as the 1920s. The southernmost basin contains surface expressions of hydrocarbon waste material, which is overlain by a thin layer of soil or biotic crust. This basin may have received oil skim from the Refinery canals and oil/water separator solids from a former above-ground storage tank. According to historic aerial photos, the southern portion of WMU 31 may have received material from the dredging of Refinery canals. WMU 32 and the surrounding area contained north- and south-trending drainage canals at one time which may have received solid and liquid waste. The drainage canals may have been part of an early wastewater system utilized during the 1950s and 1960s. Fill material, possibly from the West Canal, were placed adjacent to the West Canal on the eastern edge of WMU 32. The drainages and canals were filled in during the 1970s and 1980s.

Contaminants in the WMUs

The WMUs currently include contamination that the State and Federal agencies with jurisdiction over the project site have determined needs to be remediated. The California Regional Water Quality Control Board Order No. R2-2004-0056 includes the following descriptions of the WMUs that are proposed for clean-up:

WMU 10 Oily Sludge Land Farm

WMU 10 is an unlined inactive, 10.4-acre land-farm made up of two cells that operated from 1966-1976. The land treatment unit received approximately 10,600 cubic yards of oily wastes, and waste from the American Petroleum Institute separator and dissolved air flotation units. The unit is located in the 100-year flood plain, and is protected from flooding by 3 to 4-foot high dikes constructed around the perimeter. Depth to groundwater beneath the unit ranges from 1 to 7 feet below ground surface. The unit's waste contains petroleum hydrocarbons, metals (*i.e.*, lead and chromium), tetraethyl lead, and various organic compounds. Groundwater monitoring in the vicinity of the unit has detected lead, arsenic, and petroleum hydrocarbons. During the wet season, ponded water can be found on the unit. Interim measures to mitigate this condition include the application of a fiber-bonded matrix to minimize dust and physical contact and the pumping of ponded water from the unit. The unit does not have a soil cover, and therefore, contains exposed waste.

WMU 11 Oily Sludge Land Farm

WMU 11 is an unlined and inactive 7.2-acre land farm with a period of disposal from 1966-1976. The land treatment unit received oily wastes, petroleum sludges, and waste from the American Petroleum Institute separator and dissolved air flotation units. This unit is located in the 100-year flood plain, and is protected from flooding by the dikes constructed around the perimeter. The unit's waste contains petroleum hydrocarbons, metals (*i.e.*, lead and chromium), tetraethyl lead, and various organic compounds. Groundwater monitoring in the vicinity of the unit has detected lead, chromium, arsenic, and petroleum hydrocarbons. During the wet season, ponded water can be found on the unit. Interim measures to mitigate this condition include the application of a fiber-bonded matrix to minimize dust and physical contact. In addition, ponded water is pumped from the unit to the Refinery's water treatment plant. The unit does not have a cover, and therefore contains exposed waste.

WMU 14 Oily Sludge Land Farm

WMU 14 is an unlined inactive, 9.1-acre pond system that was constructed over the western portion of WMU 10 in 1976. The unit is made up of four sludge-drying beds that received sludge until the late 1970's from biologically treated refinery wastewater. This unit is located in the 100-year flood plain, and is protected from flooding by 2 to 5 foot high dikes constructed around the perimeter of the unit. However, during the wet season the unit may contain ponded water. The unit's waste contains petroleum hydrocarbons, metals (*i.e.*, lead, selenium, and chromium), tetraethyl lead, and various organic compounds. Groundwater monitoring in the vicinity of the unit has detected arsenic, lead, chromium, hexavalent chromium, and petroleum hydrocarbons. During the wet season, ponded water can be found on the unit. Interim measures to mitigate this condition include the application of a fiber-bonded matrix to minimize dust and physical contact

and the pumping of ponded water from the unit. The unit does not have a cover, and therefore contains exposed waste.

WMU 31 Oil Sludge Landfill

WMU 31 is an approximately 21-acre unlined and inactive landfill, with a period of disposal from the 1950s to 1960s. A tetraethyl lead blending facility was located on the west side of the unit, and may have impacted the unit. Adjacent to the site is a former drum storage area and oil skim ponds. The unit received oily wastes and dredge spoils from the former Oily Water Canal. This unit is underlain by up to 6.5 feet of oily sludge and is partially underlain by free-phase petroleum hydrocarbons. During wet weather, portions of the unit may pond. The unit's waste contains petroleum hydrocarbons, metals (*i.e.*, lead), tetraethyl lead, and various organic compounds. Groundwater monitoring in the vicinity of the unit has detected lead, chromium, zinc, and petroleum hydrocarbons. The site currently contains former ponds, pits, and an open tank with petroleum waste. Other waste in the form of glass and rubbish is evident. The unit does not have a cover, and therefore, in general, contains exposed waste.

WMU 32

WMU 32 is a 10.7-acre area located adjacent to WMU 16. There are impacts to the area that indicate that releases have occurred. A drum reconditioning facility was located 700 feet east of the unit where historical aerial photographs reveal stockpiles containing thousands of drums. The unit's area at one time contained north and south trending drainage canals, which may have received oily and contaminated water. The unit is partially underlain by free-phase petroleum hydrocarbons, which likely emanates from the Tract 3 tank farm. The unit has recently been the subject of further investigation and interim corrective measures to mitigate low pH conditions. The unit's waste contains petroleum hydrocarbons, metals (*i.e.*, lead), tetraethyl lead, low pH soil, and various organic compounds. Groundwater monitoring in the vicinity of the unit has detected arsenic, nickel, chromium, zinc, benzene, and other petroleum hydrocarbons. Low pH has also been reported in groundwater beneath the unit.

Tesoro WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32 Closure Project Area

Land uses in areas surrounding the action area include a mix of open space and various public and private uses including heavy industry, railways, residential (Cities of Clyde and Concord), commercial, Pacheco Slough to the west, and brackish marshes that connect to Hastings Slough to the north and at the Point Edith Wildlife Area adjacent to Suisun Bay (Figure 1). Other land uses in the vicinity include refineries and waste disposal, including the former IT Corporation Baker Facility, the ACME Fill Corporation Landfill, and the former Vine Hill Complex hazardous waste disposal facility. The habitats within the action area are summarized below.

Disturbed/Developed/Bare Areas

Developed roads and levees occur throughout the action area. These roads are lightly trafficked and are unsealed gravel or dirt surfaced. Bare areas devoid of vegetation occur in the basin bottoms and are scattered throughout portions of the action area. Berms and levees separate former treatment cells and are present in WMUs 10/11/14 and 31. These are steep-sided (greater than 20 percent slope), generally 3 to 5-feet tall and support ruderal grassland habitat. The roads,

levees and bare areas within the action area near WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32 provide pathways for potential predators of the salt marsh harvest mouse. Salt marsh harvest mice generally avoid developed areas devoid of vegetation. Salt marsh harvest mice, however, may forage and disperse through the ruderal grassland areas along the levees within the action area.

Disturbed Brackish Seasonal Wetland

A disturbed brackish seasonal wetland is present in the action area, including WMU interiors. The WMU interiors support vegetation typically found in these types of wetlands. Disturbed, brackish seasonal wetland communities occur in swales and depressions that become ponded or saturated during the rainy season for sufficient duration to support vegetation adapted to wetland conditions. In addition, some of the seasonal wetlands located along the northern boundary of the WMUs 10/11/14 action area appear to be subjected to tidal inundation during extreme high tide events. Disturbed brackish seasonal wetlands are located in depressions, with their boundaries delineated by changes in vegetation and by berms. Some of the brackish seasonal wetlands exhibited surface hydrology indicators such as salt crusts, biotic crusts, and sediment deposits, while others were indicated as having wetland hydrology by the presence of oxidized rhizospheres.

Dominant plant species in these wetlands include pickleweed, saltgrass, sparscale, and rabbitsfoot grass. Species interspersed with the saltgrass north of WMUs 10/11/14, north and south areas of the action area near WMU 31, and in the southwest section of WMU 32 include pickleweed, non-native Mediterranean barley, and the native saltmarsh sand spurry. Several patches of bulrush and Baltic rush are located in channels and depressions in the action area near WMUs 31 and 32. Smaller seasonal wetland areas generally support a higher cover of exotic invasive species; these areas are dominated by saltgrass, Italian ryegrass, perennial pepperweed, common sow thistle, and, in some cases, poverty weed.

Disturbed brackish seasonal wetlands north of WMUs 10/11/14 receive tidal input during extreme high tides. Due to the local hydrology, the waters cannot retreat during low tides. Within the action area near WMUs 10/11/14 and 32, disturbed brackish seasonal wetlands are small, discontinuous, and the vegetation is generally short and patchy. Within the action area near WMU 31, disturbed seasonal brackish wetlands are larger and more densely vegetated than in the action area near WMUs 10/11/14 and 32. Salt marsh harvest mice may forage and disperse through the disturbed seasonal brackish wetlands throughout the action area. Disturbed seasonal brackish wetlands with a higher density of pickleweed cover within the action area may also support breeding salt marsh harvest mice.

Disturbed Seasonal Wetland

Disturbed seasonal wetlands are present in the action area near WMU 10/11/14, including WMU interiors. The WMU interiors support vegetation typically found in these types of wetlands. Disturbed seasonal wetlands are present in the action area near WMUs 10/11/14 and are absent from the action area near WMUs 31 and 32. WMUs 10/11/14 are comprised of a series of bermed treatment cells historically used to treat and contain refinement waste. The basin bottoms of these cells have been layered with a geo-textile mat, are inundated for portions of the wet season, and support marginal hydrophytic vegetation. Some areas are devoid of vegetation. Pumping of ponded surface water occurs during the rainy season at WMUs 10/11/14 when

inundation occurs. Soils are mainly comprised of fill and degraded soil substrate. Seasonal wetland plant communities occur in swales and depressions that are ponded during the rainy season for sufficient duration to support vegetation adapted to wetland conditions. Seasonal wetlands in the action area are located in the basin bottoms. Typical plant species observed in seasonal wetlands in the action area include Italian ryegrass and rabbitsfoot grass. Based on the disturbed nature of the soils, short, unpredictable periods of inundation (multiple cycles of wetting and drying each year), sparse vegetation, and lack of hydrologic connectivity with other wetlands, the disturbed seasonal wetlands within the action area are considered poor quality habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse. Salt marsh harvest mice may forage and disperse through the disturbed seasonal wetlands throughout the action area.

Disturbed Brackish Seasonal Marsh

Disturbed brackish seasonal marsh is present in the action area near WMU 32, including the WMU 32 interior. One section of disturbed brackish seasonal marsh dominated by cattail is present in the action area near WMU 32. This long, narrow marsh runs north/south up to the northern action area boundary. The cattail within this marsh ranges between 2 to 5 feet tall. There is a dense stand of spearscale at the northern end of this marsh. The disturbed brackish seasonal marsh in the northern portion of the action area near WMU 32 is relatively small and lacks depth or connectivity to surrounding wetlands. The vegetation within this area is shorter and less dense than in adjacent undisturbed marsh areas. Salt marsh harvest mice may forage and disperse through the disturbed brackish seasonal marsh throughout the action area.

Ruderal Grassland

Ruderal grassland is present in the action area including WMU interiors. Ruderal vegetation is comprised of ruderal grass and herbaceous species. The dominant species observed in this community type were annual exotic grasses including soft chess, ripgut brome, Mediterranean barley, and Italian ryegrass. Significant areas of native, halophytic saltgrass are also included in this community if they did not exhibit characteristics of wetland habitat. Exotic ruderal herbaceous species also common in these fields included yellow star thistle, perennial pepperweed, prickly lettuce, common sow thistle, fennel, and bull thistle, with some inclusions of coyote brush, iceplant, and date palm. Salt marsh harvest mice may forage and disperse through all ruderal grasslands within the action area that are contiguous with and within 328 feet of suitable brackish seasonal wetland and brackish marsh habitat (Service 2010).

Coyote Brush Scrub

Coyote brush scrub is present in the action area near WMU 31 and 32 interiors. The action area near WMU 31 has several dense patches of coyote brush scrub along the unit perimeter berms. The action area near WMU 10/11/14 and 32 contains sporadic patches or single plants along the berms or upland areas. In this community, the understory consists of ruderal or wetland species similar to the rest of the action area, with a dominant shrub layer of coyote brush. Scattered date palms are also present in this community near the berms. Dense patches of scrub habitat provide perching and potential nesting habitat for white-tailed kites, a known predator of the salt marsh harvest mouse. The scattered date palms within WMUs 31 and 32 provide potential roosting habitat for barn owls, a known predator of salt marsh harvest mice. Although barn owls were not observed within WMUs 31 or 32, they have been seen utilizing date palms in this fashion in

other portions of the Refinery. Although coyote brush scrub may support predators of the salt marsh harvest mice, salt marsh harvest mice may forage and disperse through the herbaceous understory of coyote brush scrub habitat.

Bare Areas (Non-wetland Waters)

Bare areas (non-wetland waters) are present in the action area near the WMUs. Bare areas in the action area support sparse emergent and aquatic vegetation and algae. Bare areas were mapped based on hydrology indicators and the presence of less than five percent vegetation. Bare depressions with salt or biotic crusts that did not appear to contain substantial waste near the soil surface (*i.e.*, possessed a soil matrix dominated by fill and/or native soils) were mapped as bare areas. These depressions did not contain surface water at the time of surveys. However, these features exhibited clear signs of ponding and drying cycles, such as salt and biotic crusts, and were surrounded by areas identified as wetlands. These habitats are ephemeral, and fed primarily through rainfall. Surface runoff from rain events travels across the high-salinity soils in the area, depositing salts to these low-lying ephemeral pools. Salt marsh harvest mice typically avoid areas devoid of vegetation; however, salt marsh harvest mice have been observed nesting and sheltering in the cracks in unvegetated salt panne habitat in Suisun Marsh.

Point Edith Wildlife Area

The Point Edith Wildlife Area is located outside of but adjacent to the proposed project footprint of WMUs 10/11/14 and 31 (Figure 1). The Point Edith Wildlife Area contains high quality tidal marsh habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail. The tidal marsh of the Point Edith Wildlife Area is separated from the grasslands and seasonal wetlands of WMUs 10/11/14 and 31 by levees and the Clean Water Canal. A railroad is located on a levee between the Point Edith Wildlife Area and WMUs 10/11/14. An acoustic study conducted for the proposed project shows average ambient noise levels (L_{eq}) along the levee adjacent to the tidal marsh of the Point Edith Wildlife Area ranging from 48 decibels to 58 decibels and maximum ambient noise levels (L_{max}) ranging from 57 decibels to 74 decibels (M. Carr, Extant Acoustical Consulting, LLC, *in litt.* 2014). The highest maximum ambient noise levels at the Point Edith Wildlife Area are near WMUs 10/11/14 and are associated with railroad traffic. Ambient noise levels are lower in the Point Edith Wildlife Area adjacent to WMU 31 because the railroad is further from the tidal marsh; ambient noise in the tidal marsh next to WMU 31 is dominated by Refinery operations.

Cordelia Slough Preserve

Wildlands' Cordelia Slough Preserve is located at the former Green Lodge Duck Club property about 8.0 miles north of the action area for the proposed project on the west side of the Suisun Marsh in southwestern Solano County, California, east of Interstate 680 at the end of Goodyear Road, approximately five miles south of the City of Fairfield. The Cordelia Slough Preserve is located in a rural area of Suisun Marsh where the primary land use is duck and hunting clubs. It is bordered by a levee and Cordelia Slough to the south and east, a levee to the north, and Union Pacific Railroad tracks to the east. The Cordelia Slough Preserve is managed marsh habitat that currently supports a mosaic of pickleweed. The site also has upland habitats on the levees and full tidal habitats in the slough along the outboard levee.

The vegetative cover varies from dense stands of pickleweed to dense cover of facultative wetland species such as creeping wild rye, fat hen, and alkali heath and limited stands of salt grass. Habitats within the Cordelia Slough Preserve include semi-permanent open water, pickleweed-dominated managed marsh, upland refugia, tidal marsh (along the outboard levee), transition zone/refugia, and levee/refugia (Wildlands 2015). The diked, managed salt marsh habitats and adjacent grasslands of the Cordelia Slough Preserve provide suitable habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse. The diked salt marsh is not suitable habitat for California clapper rail since it is non-tidal. However, the tidal marshes and slough along the outboard levee of the Cordelia Slough Preserve may provide foraging and dispersal habitat for the California clapper rail.

Wildlands purchased in fee title from the Green Lodge Land Company the 195-acre property which contains the Cordelia Slough Preserve and developed a final long-term management plan for the site for the benefit of the salt marsh harvest mouse (Cordelia Slough Long-term Management Plan, Wildlands 2015). The Service approved the Final Cordelia Slough Preserve Long-term Management Plan in February 2015 (Wildlands 2015). The Cordelia Slough Preserve will provide a substantial area of protected salt marsh habitat in an area that lies between other existing conservation parcels within the Suisun Marsh. Wildlands will manage water levels across the entire 195-acre property (aside from the area currently occupied by the duck club facilities) for the benefit of salt marsh harvest mice at the Cordelia Slough Preserve. However, management activities as described in the Cordelia Slough Preserve Long-term Management Plan will only occur within the Preserve. Wildlands submitted the first annual monitoring report for the Cordelia Slough Preserve to the Service in January 2017 (Wildlands 2016).

Portions of the 195-acre Cordelia Slough Preserve property are being utilized as habitat compensation for effects to salt marsh harvest mouse from other projects in the Martinez area of Contra Costa County. For example, the preservation and management in perpetuity of a total of 7.737 acres of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat at the Cordelia Slough Preserve will compensate for the effects of the Tesoro Amorco Pipeline Support Repair and Pipeline Demolition Project, the Plains Products Terminals LLC's Line 191 Relocation Project, and ART's Monitoring Well Installations at the Refinery along Waterfront Road near the City of Martinez, Contra Costa County, California (Service file number 08ESMF00-2014-F-0108-R001, Service 2017). The preservation of an additional 13.5 acres of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat at the Cordelia Slough Preserve will compensate for the effects of the Contra Costa Water District's Shortcut Pipeline Improvement Project (Service file number 08ESMF00-2015-F-0008-R001, Service 2016).

Sonoma Creek Marsh Enhancement Project

The Sonoma Creek Marsh consists of about 402 acres of fringing tidal marsh habitat at the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge in Sonoma County, California, along the western bank of lower Sonoma Creek south of Highway 37 and east of Tubbs Island. The marsh impounds water over a 100-acre area within the southern part of the marsh for long periods following high tides and winter rains. Interior berms and historic mosquito ditches, combined with rapid marsh expansion over the last century, have likely contributed to the expansion of these impoundments. The impoundment of water leads to high mosquito production rates and reduced health of marsh vegetation resulting in a large pickleweed "die back" zone consisting of low growing dead or dying pickleweed. These conditions reduce habitat quality for a number of tidal marsh species,

especially those that primarily inhabit the pickleweed plain, such as salt marsh harvest mice and California clapper rails. However, both the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail have been observed within the northern part of Sonoma Creek Marsh downstream of the Highway 37 bridge outside of the pickleweed “die back” zone (San Francisco Estuary Institute, <http://www.sfei.org/content/salt-marsh-harvest-mouse-database-and-maps#sthash.WTXwQppi.dpbs>; CDFW 2017; Block 2010a; Block 2010b).

The San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge is working with the Marin/Sonoma Mosquito and Vector Control District to develop long-term solutions to improving drainage to this area in an effort to reduce mosquito management efforts (e.g., treatment with pesticides). The San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge and the Marin/Sonoma Mosquito and Vector Control District are proposing to enhance 265 acres of the Sonoma Creek tidal marsh by excavating channels to improve tidal circulation in the Sonoma Creek Marsh Enhancement Project (Wetlands and Water Resources, Inc. 2009; San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge 2014; Service file number 81420-2011-F-0774-2, Service 2014). The Sonoma Creek Marsh Enhancement Project will also create high-tide refugia habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail. The first phase of the Sonoma Creek Marsh Enhancement Project was constructed in 2015. Tesoro contributed \$260,000 for the restoration of at 4 acres of California clapper rail habitat in the first phase of the Sonoma Creek Marsh Enhancement Project as compensatory habitat mitigation for the effects of the Tesoro Proposed Avon Marine Oil Terminal Engineering and Maintenance Standards Compliance Project (Service file number 08FBTD00-2014-F-0023-2, Service 2015).

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Habitats and Occurrences near the Action Area for the Tesoro WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32 Closure Project

The California Natural Diversity Database (CNDDDB) reports the salt marsh harvest mouse as occurring adjacent to the action area in the tidal marsh of the Point Edith Wildlife Area across Waterfront Road from WMUs 10/11/14 and across the Clean Water Canal from WMU 31 (CNDDDB occurrence number 4, CDFW 2017). This area is identified by the CNDDDB as “Avon-Port Chicago Marsh” and includes the entire Point Edith Wildlife Area, where the species was first reported in 1971 and captured throughout the 1980s and 1990s. Salt marsh harvest mouse was last reported within the action area at the Point Edith Wildlife Area in September 1998 (CNDDDB occurrence number 4, CDFW 2017). No surveys have been conducted for the salt marsh harvest mouse near the action area since 1998. The CNDDDB also reports the salt marsh harvest mouse as occurring within tidal marsh habitat across the 285-foot-wide Pacheco Creek from WMU 32 about 450 feet west of the action area (CNDDDB occurrence number 62, CDFW 2017).

The San Francisco Estuary Institute reports the following survey data for salt marsh harvest mice within 600 feet of the action area (<http://www.sfei.org/content/salt-marsh-harvest-mouse-database-and-maps#sthash.WTXwQppi.dpbs>; San Francisco Estuary Institute, undated):

1. Twelve salt marsh harvest mice captured during 150 trapping nights in tidal marsh habitat in the Point Edith Wildlife Area about 600 feet east of WMU 31 (capture efficiency (CE) = 8.0; site 2; Schaub, CDFW, unpubl. data, 1971); and

2. Seven salt marsh harvest mouse captured during 697 trapping nights in diked marsh habitat within the action area immediately north of the Refinery at Tesoro WMU 31 (CE = 1.0; site number 252; H.T. Harvey and Associates, unpubl. data, 1997). However, this occurrence of the salt marsh harvest mouse at WMU 31 may have been reported in error. When an inquiry was made by WRA to Dr. Howard Shellhammer about the location, Dr. Shellhammer stated that he had never trapped salt marsh harvest mice within the Tosco (now Tesoro Golden Eagle) Refinery, and that the location information must have been reported incorrectly (H. Shellhammer, H.T. Harvey and Associates, pers. comm. 2009 cited in WRA 2014).

The brackish seasonal wetlands within the action area that contain pickleweed provide suitable breeding, foraging, and dispersal habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse. The salt marsh harvest mouse may also forage and disperse through all ruderal grassland and seasonal wetland habitats that are contiguous with and within 328 feet of suitable brackish seasonal wetland habitat. On the basis of habitat assessment and the proximity of known records, the Service believes the salt marsh harvest mouse is likely to occur within all suitable brackish seasonal wetland habitat within the action area and all adjacent ruderal upland and seasonal wetland habitat within 328 feet of suitable brackish seasonal wetland habitat in WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32. Figure 1 shows the location of suitable salt marsh harvest mouse habitat within the action area.

Table 1 below summarizes the amount of suitable wetland and upland habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse that occurs within the action area in each of the WMUs. Out of the 110-acre action area within the WMUs, about 53.07 acres (48 percent) is suitable habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse (22.29 acres of wetland habitat and 30.78 acres of upland habitat). WMUs 10/11/14 contain about 13.91 acres of suitable salt marsh harvest mouse habitat (5.14 acres of wetland habitat and 8.77 acres of upland habitat). WMU 31 contains about 31.76 acres of suitable salt marsh harvest mouse habitat (14.79 acres of wetland habitat and 16.97 acres of upland habitat). WMU 32 contains about 7.40 acres of suitable salt marsh harvest mouse habitat (2.36 acres of wetland habitat and 5.04 acres of upland habitat).

Habitat within the action area is largely considered low quality due to the structure of vegetation present, the limited expanse of year-round vegetative cover, the seasonal nature of the vegetation communities within all of the WMUs, and the presence of contaminants. The WMUs are dominated by seasonal, non-native grassland communities which do not provide cover or sources of food year-round due to seasonal vegetation die-back, and there is no evidence in the available literature to suggest that these areas are used by salt marsh harvest mouse as more than opportunistic or seasonal habitat (Fisler 1965; Johnson and Shellhammer 1988; Service 2010).

Table 1. Suitable salt marsh harvest mouse habitat within the action area.

Work Area	Wetland Habitat (acres)	Upland Habitat (acres)	Total Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse Habitat (acres)
WMUs 10/11/14	5.14	8.77	13.91
WMU 31	14.79	16.97	31.76
WMU 32	2.36	5.04	7.40
TOTAL	22.29	30.78	53.07

Despite the overall low quality of potential habitat within the WMUs, there is a moderate potential that the WMUs could support a population of the salt marsh harvest mouse. The action area could have occasional, opportunistic spillover from surrounding potential habitat areas. A source population of the salt marsh harvest mouse could persist within densely vegetated areas of the WMUs.

Occurrences near Cordelia Slough Preserve

The CNDDDB reports the occurrence of the salt marsh harvest mouse at the Roos Club about 3,200 feet northeast of the Cordelia Slough Preserve (CNDDDB occurrence number 179; CDFW 2017). The San Francisco Estuary Institute reports the following survey data for salt marsh harvest mice within 2,500 feet of the Cordelia Slough Preserve (<http://www.sfei.org/content/salt-marsh-harvest-mouse-database-and-maps#sthash.WTXwQppi.dpbs>; San Francisco Estuary Institute, undated): 18 salt marsh harvest mouse captured during 284 trapping nights in diked marsh habitat at Goodyear Slough about 2,500 feet west of the proposed Cordelia Slough Preserve (CE = 6.34; site number 446; California Department of Water Resources and CDFW, unpubl. data, 1999).

Surveys for the salt marsh harvest mouse were conducted by the U.S. Geological Survey in April 2009 on the duck club property adjacent to the northeastern edge of the Cordelia Slough Preserve (U.S. Geological Survey 2009). The salt marsh harvest mouse was found on the first night at four out of the five trap locations across the adjacent duck club property site, and a total of nine individuals were captured. Of these, a female salt marsh harvest mouse was in early breeding condition and three of the males were in reproductive condition. Two of the salt marsh harvest mice were captured within 660 feet northeast of the Cordelia Slough Preserve. U.S. Geological Survey personnel concluded that the captures per trap nights indicates a relatively large population of salt marsh harvest mouse at the adjacent duck club property in comparison with other sites in northern San Pablo Bay, and that the timing of these captures in early spring indicates that this site has a resident population rather than transient dispersing individuals. In addition, it was noted that the presence of reproductively mature individuals indicates that the site is being used as a breeding source (U.S. Geological Survey 2009 cited in Wildlands 2013).

Five salt marsh harvest mice were captured during 100 trapping nights at the Cordelia Slough Preserve in June 2014 (K. Allan, WRA, *in litt.* 2014). Salt marsh harvest mice were captured within the following habitat types at the Cordelia Slough Preserve: pickleweed-dominated managed marsh, invasive pepperweed-dominated refugia habitat, and common reed-dominated tidal marsh (K. Allan, WRA, *in litt.* 2014). Due to known recent occurrence of the salt marsh harvest mouse at the Cordelia Slough Preserve, the proximity to other occurrences, and the availability of suitable high quality pickleweed marsh habitat at the Cordelia Slough Preserve,

the Service believes the salt marsh harvest mouse is likely to occur within all suitable habitat at the Cordelia Slough Preserve.

Suisun Bay Area Recovery Unit

The proposed project and the Cordelia Slough Preserve occur within the Recovery Plan's Suisun Bay Area recovery unit for the salt marsh harvest mouse (Service 2013a). The Suisun Bay Area recovery unit is within the range of the northern subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse (*R. r. halicoetes*) (Service 2013a). The Suisun Bay Area recovery unit includes suitable or restorable tideland habitats in the Suisun Bay area from Carquinez Strait to the edge of the Sacramento-San Joaquin River Delta (Delta) (legal Delta boundary), representing the eastern extent of the range of the salt marsh harvest mouse. It is separated from the San Pablo Bay recovery unit by gaps in habitat in the Carquinez Strait and intervening hills. Limited populations of salt marsh harvest mouse exist within the Suisun Bay Area recovery unit.

The action area for the proposed project occurs near one of the largest and most stable populations of the salt marsh harvest mouse within the Suisun Bay Area recovery unit (the tidal marshes along the Contra Costa County shoreline between Point Edith and Middle Point) (Service 2013a). The Recovery Plan (page 260, Figure III-8, Segment B; Service 2013a) identifies Hastings Slough immediately east of the proposed project area as a priority area for likely future tidal marsh restoration.

The Cordelia Slough Preserve occurs within the Western Suisun/Hill Slough marsh complex of the Suisun Bay Area recovery unit. One of the criteria in the Recovery Plan for the downlisting of the salt marsh harvest mouse to threatened is for the protection, management, and restoration of at least 1,000 acres of suitable marsh habitat within the Western Suisun/Hill Slough marsh complex including five viable habitat areas each 150 acres or more in size (Table III-3 in Service 2013a). The proposed preservation of the diked wetlands within the Cordelia Slough Preserve could count toward the downlisting criteria for the protection, management, and restoration of suitable marsh habitat within the Western Suisun/Hill Slough marsh complex. However, the preservation of the diked wetlands of the Cordelia Slough Preserve would not count toward the downlisting criteria for the protection of a viable habitat area as defined in the Recovery Plan unless the diked wetlands were restored to tidal marsh (Service 2013a).

The proposed Sonoma Creek Marsh Enhancement Project at the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge occurs within the Recovery Plan's San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit for salt marsh harvest mouse (Service 2013a).

Suisun Marsh Habitat Management, Preservation and Restoration Plan

On April 21, 2014, the U.S. Bureau of Reclamation and the Service issued the Record of Decision for the *Suisun Marsh Habitat Management, Preservation and Restoration Plan* (U.S. Bureau of Reclamation and Service 2014). The *Suisun Marsh Habitat Management, Preservation and Restoration Plan* is a comprehensive 30-year framework for a broad partnership to restore 5,000 to 7,000 acres of marsh to tidal wetlands and protect and enhance more than 40,000 acres of managed wetlands within the Suisun Marsh near the City of Fairfield, Solano County, California (U.S. Bureau of Reclamation, Service, and CDFW 2013). The objectives of the *Suisun Marsh Habitat Management, Preservation and Restoration Plan* include

improving habitat for multiple special-status species including the salt marsh harvest mouse; maintaining the heritage of waterfowl hunting and other recreational opportunities; improving water quality to assist fish migration and spawning; and improving and maintaining the levee system to protect property, infrastructure, and wildlife habitats from flooding. The Cordelia Slough Preserve occurs within Suisun Marsh Region 1 of the *Suisun Marsh Habitat Management, Preservation and Restoration Plan* area (Figure 2 in U.S. Bureau of Reclamation, Service, and CDFW 2013). Between 8.4 and 12.6 percent (1,000 to 1,500 acres) of existing managed wetlands within Suisun Marsh Region 1 will be restored to tidal marsh within 30 years under the *Suisun Marsh Habitat Management, Preservation and Restoration Plan* (Table 2 in U.S. Bureau of Reclamation, Service, and CDFW 2013).

California Clapper Rail

California clapper rails are unlikely to occur within the diked seasonal wetlands and grasslands within the proposed project footprint because the wetlands are not tidal. However, California clapper rails may occur infrequently within the action area in the tidal marsh of the adjacent Point Edith Wildlife Area near WMUs 31 and 10/11/14. A California clapper rail was last detected within the action area in the tidal marsh of the adjacent Point Edith Wildlife Area in 2009 when an individual was observed (by vocalization) moving through the tidal marsh near WMU 31 (WRA 2016a, 2016b). No other California clapper rails have been detected within 700 feet of the proposed project footprint during protocol-level surveys conducted during nine consecutive years (2009-2017) at WMU 31 and four consecutive years (2014-2017) at WMUs 10/11/14 and 32 (WRA 2008a, 2008c, 2008d, 2009f, 2009g, 2009h, 2011b, 2012b, 2013b, 2014b, 2015, 2016a, 2016b). Based on the known occurrence of the California clapper rail within the action area in 2009 and the availability of suitable tidal marsh breeding habitat within the adjacent Point Edith Wildlife Area, it is likely that a breeding pair of California clapper rails will occur within the action area at the adjacent Point Edith Wildlife Area during the proposed project's six-year construction period.

The proposed project occurs within the Recovery Plan's Suisun Bay Area Recovery Unit for the California clapper rail (Service 2013a). California clapper rails are present sporadically and in low numbers at various locations throughout the Suisun Marsh area. The proposed Sonoma Creek Marsh Enhancement Project at the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge occurs within the Recovery Plan's San Pablo Bay Recovery Unit for the California clapper rail (Service 2013a).

Effects of the Action

Direct effects of the proposed project are effects occurring within the action area during construction of the proposed project. Direct effects may be temporary (habitat restored to pre-project conditions within 24 months of the initial disturbance) or permanent (lasting more than 24 months). Indirect effects are the effects of the proposed project generally occurring later in time after construction has been completed (*e.g.*, degradation of habitat due to the spread of invasive plant species). The direct and indirect effects of the proposed project on the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail are summarized below.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse*Habitat Disturbance*

Areas of suitable salt marsh harvest mouse habitat that will be temporarily disturbed or permanently lost are illustrated in the map in Figure 1. Table 2 below summarizes the amount of habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse that will be temporarily disturbed or permanently lost by the proposed project within each WMU. The proposed project will result in the temporary disturbance of a total of 5.46 acres of suitable wetland habitat and 19.18 acres of suitable upland habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse. The proposed project will result in the permanent loss of a total of 2.96 acres of suitable wetland habitat and 8.31 acres of suitable upland habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse. The proposed project will avoid the disturbance of 17.16 acres of suitable habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse within the WMUs within the 110-acre project area (Figure 1).

Table 2. Salt marsh harvest mouse habitat disturbance.

Work Area	Wetland Habitat (acres)	Upland Habitat (acres)	Total Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse Habitat (acres)
Temporary Disturbance			
WMUs 10/11/14	2.47	4.41	6.88
WMU 31	2.99	14.77	17.76
WMU 32	0.00	0.00	0.00
TOTAL Temporary	5.46	19.18	24.64
Permanent Loss			
WMUs 10/11/14	0.86	3.35	4.21
WMU 31	0.00	0.00	0.00
WMU 32	2.10	4.96	7.06
TOTAL Permanent	2.96	8.31	11.27

Temporary effects will result in the temporary loss of salt marsh harvest mouse foraging and cover habitat. Construction activities associated with the removal of wastes in WMUs 10 and 11 will temporarily disturb 6.88 acres of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat. Construction activities associated with excavation and backfilling in WMU 31 will temporarily disturb about 17.76 acres of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat including the construction of an access road along the north side of WMU 31 (1.7 acres of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat disturbed), which will be restored in the uplands. Permanent loss of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat will occur as a result of the installation of a cap over WMU 14 (4.21 acres of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat lost). Construction of a cap at WMU 32 will result in the permanent loss of 7.06 acres of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat. The disturbance of suitable grassland habitat will remove habitat the salt marsh harvest mouse utilizes for foraging, dispersal, and sheltering. The disturbance of suitable wetland habitat will remove habitat the salt marsh harvest mouse utilizes for breeding, foraging, dispersal, and sheltering. Temporarily disturbed habitat within the action area will be restored to pre-construction conditions or better within 24 months of the initial disturbance under a Service-approved HMMP. Salt marsh harvest mice will also benefit in the long term from the cleanup of hazardous materials from the proposed project footprint thereby reducing their exposure to hazardous materials that could otherwise have lethal or sublethal effects on salt marsh harvest mice within the WMUs. Additionally, salt marsh harvest mice around Suisun Bay may also

benefit from the cleanup of hazardous materials from the proposed project footprint that could otherwise enter tidal marsh habitat around Suisun Bay by leaching into groundwater or during extreme flooding events or with future sea level rise.

As noted previously in the *Description of the Action* section, the project proponent has also proposed a set of conservation measures, including the commitment to provide compensatory habitat as a condition of the action. This compensatory habitat is intended to minimize the effect on the salt marsh harvest mouse of the proposed project's anticipated incidental take, resulting from the temporary disturbance and the permanent loss of habitat described above. The compensatory habitat proposed will be in the form of the preservation and management in perpetuity of 83.09 acres of suitable habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse at Wildlands' Cordelia Slough Preserve in Suisun Bay within the Suisun Bay Area recovery unit under a Service-approved long-term management plan with a fully funded endowment (Wildlands 2015). This component of the action will have the effect of protecting and managing lands for the species' conservation in perpetuity. The compensatory lands will provide suitable habitat for breeding, feeding, or sheltering commensurate with or better than habitat lost as a result of the proposed project. Providing this compensatory habitat as part of a relatively large, contiguous block of conserved land may contribute to other recovery efforts for the species. In addition, the salt marsh harvest mouse is also likely to benefit from the restoration of 5.5 acres of suitable tidal marsh/high-tide refuge habitat for the California clapper rail in the Sonoma Creek Marsh Enhancement Project at the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge within the San Pablo Bay recovery unit.

Direct Effects to Individuals

Any salt marsh harvest mice occurring within the proposed project area during construction activities could be injured or killed by being crushed by the use heavy equipment within suitable wetland and grassland habitat. Individual salt marsh harvest mice may be displaced by noise and vibrations associated with construction activities and the operation of heavy equipment within and adjacent to suitable habitat. Displaced salt marsh harvest mice may have to compete for resources in occupied habitat and may be more vulnerable to predators. Disturbance of female salt marsh harvest mice from March to November may cause abandonment or failure of the current litter. Displaced salt marsh harvest mice may suffer from increased predation, competition, mortality, and reduced reproductive success.

The type and severity of effect depends on several factors, including the intensity and characteristics of the sound, the distance of the salt marsh harvest mice from the source, the timing of actions, and the frequency and duration of the noise-generating activities. The range of effects potentially includes behavioral effects, physiological stress, physical injury, and mortality.

ART will minimize the potential for injury and mortality of salt marsh harvest mice and reduce the level of disturbance during construction activities within suitable salt marsh harvest mouse habitat by having a Service-approved biological monitor supervise the removal of all vegetation within the work area to bare ground. Prior to removal of vegetation, the biologist will walk the work zone to ensure no salt marsh harvest mice or their nests occur within the work zone. In potential salt marsh harvest mouse habitat areas, vegetation will be removed using a two-step process by which vegetation will be removed to bare ground in a manner to enable and

encourage salt marsh harvest mice to move out and away from the construction area. Tall vegetation will first be removed using a walk behind mower with the blade set at a high ground clearance to avoid direct mortality to the salt marsh harvest mouse. This will allow subsequent removal of vegetation to the ground surface using string trimmers under the supervision of a Service-approved biological monitor since visibility of the ground surface will be possible given the short stature of the vegetation. Once vegetation removal is complete, temporary exclusion fencing will be placed around a defined work area under the supervision of a Service-approved biological monitor prior to the start of construction activities preventing salt marsh harvest mice from moving into construction areas. If a salt marsh harvest mouse is encountered during construction, activities within 100 feet of the mouse will cease until the mouse leaves the work area of its own volition, and it has been determined by the biologist that the mouse will not be harmed. If the mouse does not move, the Service-approved biologist will contact the Service for guidance.

ART will minimize the potential for attracting predators of the salt marsh harvest mouse to the work area by enclosing all foods and food-related trash items in sealed trash containers and properly disposing of all trash offsite.

Construction personnel will receive Service-approved worker environmental awareness training from a Service-approved biologist. The training will include a description of the salt marsh harvest mouse, including natural history and habitat, a review of the species listing, general protection measures to be implemented to protect the species, and a delineation of the limits of the work areas.

No nighttime work is planned; however, if nighttime work is necessary the applicant will direct the lighting away from potential salt marsh harvest mouse habitat outside the exclusion fence and use lighting that minimizes backward and side lighting.

Invasive Plant Species

The proposed project has the potential to degrade salt marsh harvest mouse habitat through the introduction of invasive weeds during proposed project construction. Invasive weeds, such as perennial pepperweed, could spread into marsh habitats when seeds are attached to vehicles, equipment, and clothing. The spread of perennial pepperweed and other invasive plants can displace native marsh vegetation and lower habitat quality for salt marsh harvest mice by reducing the amount of plants they use for cover, nesting, and food, such as marsh gumplant and pickleweed. Perennial pepperweed provides poor upland refugia cover because the plant is leafless in the winter when the salt marsh harvest mouse is in most need of suitable upland refugia cover during the more frequent winter extreme high tides and storm events. Without suitable upland refugia cover, the salt marsh harvest mouse is more vulnerable to predation during extreme high tide and flooding events. ART will reduce the potential for the introduction and spread of invasive plant species by restoring all temporarily disturbed habitats with suitable native plant species under a Service-approved HMMP.

Contamination of Suitable Habitat

Suitable wetland and upland habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse could be degraded or contaminated if hazardous materials were spilled during the excavation of waste material from

the WMUs. Salt marsh harvest mice could be injured or killed if exposed to toxic substances or indirectly affected if hazardous materials degraded or stunted the growth of suitable vegetative cover the mouse utilizes for foraging, nesting, and sheltering. ART will minimize the potential for the contamination and degradation of suitable habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse during waste cleanup within the WMUs by removing and consolidating the waste materials, properly disposing of wastes off-Refinery, or consolidating and capping the wastes within the WMUs with a prescriptive Title 27 low-permeability, engineered alternative soil cap with an erosion-resistant surface of gravel, rock, or other low-growing, vegetated ground cover material. Existing surface seeps of oily waste will be excavated at WMU 32 down to the top of the groundwater table (*i.e.*, about 4 feet below ground surface), and either disposed off-Refinery or consolidated at WMU 14. The waste excavations will be backfilled with clean soil to approximately pre-excavation grades and re-vegetated. The caps of the closed WMUs will be regularly inspected, maintained, and repaired/ upgraded in accordance with SFRWQCB-approved Closure and Post-Closure Maintenance Plans. BMPs will be implemented to minimize erosion and sedimentation. Possible BMPs include, but are not limited to, silt fencing, straw wattles, and watering. Additionally, ART will implement water quality BMPs, a Storm Water Pollution Prevention Plan, and an emergency spill containment and contingency plan to minimize the potential for the degradation of suitable habitat. The proposed project will reduce the potential for the contamination of suitable salt marsh harvest mouse habitat within the WMUs and adjacent areas within the long-term by properly disposing of, consolidating, and capping the hazardous wastes under an erosion-resistant cap.

California Clapper Rail

Construction Noise

No suitable tidal marsh habitat for the California clapper rail will be directly disturbed by the proposed project. However, breeding California clapper rails in the tidal marsh of the adjacent Point Edith Wildlife Area may be disturbed by construction noise from the proposed project during the rail's breeding season. Figure 2 below illustrates the extent to which noise levels within suitable tidal marsh habitat in the adjacent Point Edith Wildlife Area will be elevated above ambient conditions due to proposed project construction noise. Suitable tidal marsh breeding habitat for the California clapper rail in the adjacent Point Edith Wildlife Area will receive noise levels elevated 8 to 13 decibels above ambient conditions due to proposed project construction (M. Carr, Extant Acoustical Consulting, LLC, *in litt.* 2014) including an area where a California clapper rail was observed in 2009 (WRA 2015). The additional noise from proposed project construction may result in California clapper rails avoiding the tidal marsh near the proposed project footprint. California clapper rails are particularly sensitive to noise disturbance during the rail's breeding season. For example, Albertson (1995) documented a California clapper rail abandoning its territory in Laumeister Marsh in south San Francisco Bay shortly after a repair crew worked on a nearby transmission tower. The rail did not establish a stable territory within the duration of the breeding season. As a result of this territorial abandonment, the opportunity for successful reproduction during the breeding season was eliminated. Thus proposed project construction during the breeding season may result in California clapper rails abandoning breeding territories near the proposed project. However, protocol-level surveys conducted within the action area between 2009 and 2017 demonstrate the lack of California

Figure 2. Estimated increase in noise levels above ambient conditions due to proposed project construction (copied from Figure 6 in M. Carr, Extant Acoustical Consulting, LLC, *in litt.* 2014).

clapper rails within the action area during recent years (WRA 2017b). A single California clapper rail was observed near WMU 31 in 2009 (WRA 2015), but no California clapper rails have been detected in the action area since 2009 during annual protocol-level surveys (WRA 2017b). Therefore, the potential for and number of breeding California clapper rails that may be harassed by proposed project construction is likely to be low. However, based on the known occurrence of a California clapper rail within the action area eight years ago and suitable tidal marsh breeding habitat remaining within the action area, the Service believes the potential for breeding California clapper rails to be disturbed during the six-year construction period is not discountable and is likely to occur. The Service estimates that no more than one breeding pair of California clapper rails will be harassed by construction noise during the six years of proposed project construction during the breeding season.

As noted previously in the *Description of the Action* section, the project proponent has also proposed a set of conservation measures, including the commitment to provide compensatory habitat as a condition of the action. This compensatory habitat is intended to minimize the effect resulting from the disturbance of a breeding pair of California clapper rails as described above. The compensatory habitat proposed will be in the form of the funding of \$357,500 for the restoration of at least 5.5 acres of suitable tidal marsh/high-tide refuge habitat for the California clapper rail in the Sonoma Creek Marsh Enhancement Project at the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge within the San Pablo Bay recovery unit under a Service-approved restoration plan. This component of the action will have the effect of restoring lands for the species' conservation in perpetuity. The compensatory lands will provide suitable habitat for breeding, feeding, or sheltering commensurate with or better than habitat at the Point Edith Wildlife Area where breeding California clapper rails may be disturbed during construction of the proposed project. Providing this compensatory habitat as part of a relatively large, contiguous block of conserved land may contribute to other recovery efforts for the species.

Remediation of Hazardous Materials

California clapper rails may also benefit from the cleanup of hazardous materials from the proposed project footprint that could otherwise enter tidal marsh habitat around Suisun Bay by leaching into groundwater or during extreme flooding events or with future sea level rise. Schwarzbach *et al.* (2003) found that California clapper rail eggs with low rates of hatchability at several marshes around San Francisco Bay showed evidence of chemical contamination. The report found that contamination appeared to exert an adverse effect on hatchability: "While all marshes had impaired hatchability, the marshes with the lowest hatchability were also adjacent to potential contaminant sources— a hazardous waste site near Laumeister and an oil refinery near Wildcat" (Schwarzbach *et al.* (2003)). Therefore, the cleanup of hazardous materials from the proposed project footprint may benefit the California clapper rail in the long-term by reducing the entry of contaminants into Suisun Bay that may reduce egg viability in California clapper rail nests around Suisun Bay.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local, or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the action area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions that are unrelated to the proposed action are not considered in this section because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. ART redesigned the

Residual Acid Tar Interim Corrective Action at WMU 32 to avoid the disturbance of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat (B. Clarke, WRA, *in litt.* 2016). However, ART's implementation of the Residual Acid Tar Interim Corrective Action at WMU 32 resulted in the accidental spill of grout into tidal marsh habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse along Pacheco Creek adjacent to WMU 32 on December 7, 2016 (T. Fitzpatrick, ART, pers. comm. 2016). Cleanup actions for the grout spill resulted in the permanent removal of about 0.002 acre of suitable wetland habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse along Pacheco Creek adjacent to WMU 32 (B. Clarke, WRA, *in litt.* 2017; M. Osowski, WRA, *in litt.* 2017b). The permanent removal of salt marsh harvest mouse wetland habitat due to the grout spill cleanup resulted in the loss of a small amount of suitable breeding, foraging, and dispersal habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse along Pacheco Creek. ART will compensate for the permanent removal of 0.002 acre of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat due to the grout spill by funding the preservation in perpetuity of 0.006 acre of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat at Wildlands' Cordelia Slough Preserve in Suisun Bay (B. Clarke, WRA, *in litt.* 2017).

Conclusion

After reviewing the current status of the salt marsh harvest mouse, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed Tesoro WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32 Closure Project, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the Tesoro WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32 Closure Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the salt marsh harvest mouse. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of precluding recovery or reducing the likelihood of survival of the species based on the following: (1) successful implementation of the conservation measures by ART and their contractors as described in this biological opinion will minimize the adverse effects on individual salt marsh harvest mice; (2) the marginal quality of the habitat that would be disturbed; (3) suitable habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse will remain onsite due to the restoration onsite of all areas temporarily disturbed under a Service-approved HMMP and the avoidance of disturbing 17.16 acres of suitable habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse within the WMUs; (4) ART's funding the preservation and management in perpetuity of at least 83.09 acres of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat within the Suisun Bay Area recovery unit under a Service-approved long-term management plan at the Cordelia Slough Preserve; and (5) ART's funding of \$357,500 for the restoration of at least 5.5 acres of tidal marsh/high tide refuge habitat at the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge.

After reviewing the current status of the California clapper rail, the environmental baseline for the action area, the effects of the proposed Tesoro WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32 Closure Project, and the cumulative effects, it is the Service's biological opinion that the Tesoro WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32 Closure Project, as proposed, is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the California clapper rail. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the environmental baseline and analyzed in consideration of all potential cumulative effects, will not rise to the level of precluding recovery or reducing the likelihood of survival of the species based on the following: (1) successful implementation of the conservation measures by ART and their contractors as described in this biological opinion will minimize the adverse effects on individual California clapper rails; (2) no suitable tidal marsh breeding habitat for the California clapper rail will be directly disturbed by the proposed project; (3) the potential for and number of breeding California clapper rails that may be harassed by

construction noise is likely to be low; and (4) ART's funding of \$357,500 for the restoration of at least 5.5 acres of tidal marsh/high tide refuge habitat for the California clapper rail at the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harass is defined by Service regulations at 50 CFR 17.3 as an intentional or negligent act or omission which creates the likelihood of injury to wildlife by annoying it to such an extent as to significantly disrupt normal behavior patterns which include, but are not limited to, breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Harm is defined by the same regulations as an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Harm is further defined to include significant habitat modification or degradation that results in death or injury to listed species by significantly impairing essential behavior patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering. Incidental take is defined as take that is incidental to, and not the purpose of, the carrying out of an otherwise lawful activity. Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not intended as part of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the terms and conditions of this Incidental Take Statement.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the applicant, as appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions or (2) fails to require the applicant to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps or ART must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR §402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

The Service anticipates incidental take of individual salt marsh harvest mice will be difficult to detect or quantify because of the variable, unknown size of any resident population over time, their elusive and cryptic behavior, and the difficulty of finding killed or injured animals. Due to the difficulty in quantifying the number of salt marsh harvest mice that will be taken as a result of the proposed project, the Service is quantifying take incidental to the proposed project as the following:

1. The harassment and non-lethal harm of all salt marsh harvest mice within the 5.46 acres of suitable wetland habitat and 19.18 acres of suitable upland habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse temporarily disturbed during construction of the proposed project.

2. The harassment and harm of all salt marsh harvest mice within the 2.96 acres of suitable wetland habitat and 8.31 acres of suitable upland habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse permanently removed during construction of the proposed project.
3. The injury or mortality of two (2) adult salt marsh harvest mice and four (4) juvenile salt marsh harvest mice.

California Clapper Rail

The Service anticipates incidental take of individual California clapper rails will be difficult to detect or quantify because of the variable, unknown size of any resident population over time, their elusive and cryptic behavior, and the difficulty of finding killed or injured animals. Due to the difficulty in quantifying the number of California clapper rails that will be taken as a result of the proposed project, the Service is quantifying take incidental to the proposed project as the following:

1. The harassment of one breeding pair of California clapper rails.

Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail associated with the Tesoro WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32 Closure Project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that this level of anticipated take is not likely to result in jeopardy to the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

Reasonable and Prudent Measures

All necessary and appropriate measures to avoid or minimize effects on the salt marsh harvest mouse resulting from implementation of this project have been incorporated into the project's proposed conservation measures. Therefore, the Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize incidental take of the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail:

1. All conservation measures, as described in the January 2017 Biological Assessment (WRA 2017a) and restated here in the *Description of the Proposed Action* section of this biological opinion, shall be fully implemented and adhered to. Further, this reasonable and prudent measure shall be supplemented by the terms and conditions below.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps must ensure compliance with the following terms and conditions, which implement the reasonable and prudent measure described above. These terms and conditions are nondiscretionary.

1. The Corps shall include full implementation and adherence to the conservation measures as a condition of any permit or contract issued for the project.
2. The Corps shall ensure that ART has a HMMP reviewed and approved by the Service no more than six months after the initiation of construction of the proposed project.
3. The Corps shall ensure that ART funds the preservation and management of at least 83.09 acres of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat at the Cordelia Slough Preserve prior to the initiation of construction of the proposed project and that a receipt is provided documenting the funding.
4. The Corps shall ensure that ART funds the \$357,500 for the restoration of at least 5.5 acres of California clapper rail habitat at the San Pablo Bay National Wildlife Refuge prior to the initiation of construction of the proposed project and that a receipt is provided documenting the funding.

Monitoring:

- a. For those components of the action that will result in habitat degradation or modification whereby incidental take in the form of harm is anticipated, the Corps shall provide a precise accounting of the total acreage of habitat impacted to the Service after completion of construction.
- b. The Corps shall immediately contact the Service's San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office (BDFWO) at (916) 930-5634 to report direct encounters between listed species and project workers and their equipment whereby incidental take in the form of harassment, harm, injury, or death occurs. If the encounter occurs after normal working hours, the Corps shall contact the BDFWO at the earliest possible opportunity the next working day. When injured or killed individuals of the listed species are found, the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the Salvage and Disposition of Individuals section below.
- c. The Corps shall provide annual reports to the Service during the post-construction monitoring period for the HMMP on the status of revegetation and invasive plant species control within the action area in meeting the success criteria.
- d. Report sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species to the CNDDDB of the CDFW.

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals:

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Program at the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office at (916) 930-5603.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

1. Restore and preserve tidal marsh and marsh ecotone/transition zone habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail within the Suisun Bay Area recovery unit along the Contra Costa County shoreline consistent with the Recovery Plan (Figures III-8 and III-9 on pp.260-261 in Service 2013).
2. Enhance salt marsh harvest mouse habitat within Wildlands' Cordelia Slough Preserve in Suisun Bay in Solano County, California.
3. Implement a predator management program, invasive plant species control plan, and marsh ecotone restoration activities on Tesoro lands within and near suitable tidal marsh habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.
4. Remove non-native trees that provide perch and nest sites for avian predators near suitable habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.
5. Control invasive plant species and plant suitable high-tide refugia cover (*e.g.*, marsh gumplant) in transition zone habitat adjacent to suitable tidal marsh habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse and California clapper rail.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION—CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation on the Tesoro WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32 Closure Project. As provided in 50 CFR §402.16, reinitiation of formal consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service where discretionary Federal agency involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:

- (a) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
- (b) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
- (c) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion; or
- (d) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

If you have any questions regarding this biological opinion on the proposed Tesoro WMUs 10/11/14, 31, and 32 Closure Project, please contact Kim Squires, Section 7 Coordinator, of the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office at the letterhead address, electronic mail (Kim_Squires@fws.gov), or at telephone (916) 930-5634, or Joseph Terry, Senior Biologist, at the Sacramento Fish and Wildlife Office, electronic mail (Joseph_Terry@fws.gov), or at telephone (916) 943-6721.

Sincerely,

A handwritten signature in black ink, appearing to read 'Kaylee Allen', with a long horizontal flourish extending to the right.

Kaylee Allen
Field Supervisor

cc:

Michael McGuire, Geosyntec Consultants, Oakland, California

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